

Machine Learning Tool for Kids : A Contribution to Teaching Computational Thinking in Schools

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Abstract - Several authors have mentioned that we are in the age of Thinking with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and that it is necessary to introduce AI, at different levels of education, in order to prepare young people for the digital society of the XXI century. The school plays a key role in achieving this objective, otherwise we are encouraging info-excluded citizens, unable to follow the professions of the future. Several world organizations note a mismatch between the curriculum and educational practices. Fortunately, Portugal has been slowly moving towards the integration and renewal of new technologies in our education system and we are in a process of digital transition. This study aims to understand the potential of AI and the correlation with Computational Thinking (CT) in an educational context, with a 9th grade class, from the 3rd Cycle of Basic Education, in a public school on the island of S. Miguel and through a machine learning activity, based on the well-known game Rock Paper Scissors, using the AI platform and tool, Machine Learning for Kids (ML4K). The methodology used in this case study is qualitative and contributed to recognize AI and machine learning as a resource for development of CT. The results achieved with the study show that the use of AI topics promotes new ideas and new knowledge in students, which can help in understanding the basic concepts of CT. These results are analyzed, discussed and related to another study in the area and confirmed according to the proposed objective.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Computational Thinking, Machine Learning, Learning Model

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the technological advances that are being felt throughout the world are transforming the society in which we live, creating forms of interaction and collaboration between humans and technology. According to Wing (2006), the ability to think computationally is not limited to just the use of technology. The acquisition of skills associated with the

CT allows people to face complex challenges, assist in their decision-making and help find solutions to solve problems in a faster, more efficient and systematic way.

The Machine Learning for Kids platform was used in the study, which aims to encourage students to explore machine learning in a playful and educational way, when students perform tasks in the field of AI. According to (Garcia *et al.*, 2019) the ML4K platform is considered a pioneering tool in teaching this subject to children and young people. Rock Paper Scissors is a hand game in which two players choose between three different options: each option can win or lose to one of the other options, and the objective of the game is to choose the option that beats the option chosen by the opponent. It's a simple and fun game that can be played anywhere with just two people. Therefore, the objective of this study is to evaluate the development of the CT, using the ML4K platform and tool, with the application of an machine learning activity and with ML4K's Scratch3, based on the Rock Paper Scissor game, with the use of a script available on the aforementioned platform (Machine Learning for Kids, 2023), adapted and translated on the Web & IA platform (Web & IA). The choice of ML4K is justified because it has a friendly and intuitive interface for children, and because it is used by several schools around the world. Regarding the structure of this document, and after the introductory chapter, a literature review is presented that supports the concepts covered. Subsequently, the methodology adopted to carry out this study is described and the results obtained in the activity are analyzed. Finally, conclusions are presented.

II. SEARCH EXPRESSION

The search expression created and tested on Google Scholar was "Machine Learning" AND "learning" AND "computational thinking". The previous search expression uses the Boolean operator AND to combine the key terms "Machine Learning for kids", "learning" and "computational thinking". The expression searches for articles that address the use of the Machine Learning for kids tool as a contribution to teaching computational thinking.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Garcia et al. (2019) the proliferation of new technologies is changing the way we live, work and learn, shaping a world where humans and technology work together to discover and innovate. The CT emerges as an important response to the impact of technology on society, helping people understand and use technology more effectively and responsibly. Yadav *et al.* (2016) emphasizes that it is essential to develop CT in students at different levels of education, as a way of preparing them for the current and future world. From the perspective of Wong *et al.* (2020) AI is a branch of computer science that is increasingly omnipresent behind the scenes of our daily lives and for Denning (2017) learning is a skill that occurs when people get involved with it and practice it. According to Caruso and Cavalheiro (2021), it is important to address AI concepts in CT activities, as a motivating element “ (...) and highlighting that the algorithms themselves, on which AI is based, intrinsically depend on the CT. Therefore, to understand how the first works, even superficially, it is necessary to have notions of the second. In a complementary way, AI is a highly motivating topic to be used in CT teaching practices in the classroom, especially for children and young people”. When students have contact with an experience associated with AI, they understand that the technology is not limited to its use; in a way, it helps them better understand the underlying AI processes in our society (Touretzky & Gardner-McCune, 2022). The AI4K12 initiative created a nationwide curriculum in the US and also globally for teaching AI, and defined it in five big ideas – Perception, Representation and Reasoning, Learning, Natural Interaction and Social Impact (Touretzky *et al.*, 2019). Learning has three categories – Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning and Reinforcement Learning. Supervised learning is a machine learning technique in which a model is trained on a set of classified data, where each sample is associated with a pre-determined label or class. The objective of supervised learning is to learn the relationship between input variables and output variables, so that the model can predict the output for new samples that were not seen during training (Saravanan & Sujatha, 2018).

IV. MACHINE LEARNING FOR KIDS

Among the various platforms on the Web, in addition to Google’s Teachable Machine, there is ML4K. The ML4K platform was developed by Dane Lane (former AI programmer at IBM) and is supported by an IBM Watson API. It is free, which allows children and teachers to adapt its use to their specific needs and was created to help children learn machine learning in a fun and educational way, using a simple and intuitive interface. Using the ML4K platform in teaching can help promote the inclusion of children with different

abilities, because it is accessible and easy to use. The platform helps children stimulate their creativity, critical thinking and programming in a visual programming language, which contributes to the creation of machine learning solutions to problems and interactive experiences. ML4K has been used in schools around the world, enabling children to create machine learning models, for example, such as image recognition and as a project in Scratch, MIT APP Inventor and Python. It also supports different languages, enabling the integration of children from different countries with different cultures.

Fig. 1. ML4K Home Page with Login option

Fig. 2. ML4K management page, where teachers can manage access and supervise learning models.

As can be seen in figure 1, the platform’s home page is shown and figure 2 shows the management options for the teacher, after logging in.

V. ROCK PAPER SCISSORS GAME

This game consists of playing with three shapes made with your hand: Rock – Closed Hand; Paper – Open hand; Scissors – index and middle fingers visible. The objective of the game is to play by trying to guess in advance the shape of the hand, which our opponent will do in the next move, with

rock beating scissors, paper beating rock and scissors beating paper.

Fig. 3. Hand Shapes of Rock Paper and Scissors

VI. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used is the qualitative case study, and is used as a data collection technique, the interview of the structured type (which was previously validated with 2 students), with audio recording and registration in a digital form. The list of questions is identical to the interviews and the respective topics. The list of interview topics is presented.

Interview – Content Exploration Topics

Machine Learning Examples (Artificial Intelligence)

- Master Algorithm
- Decision Tree
- Neural Networks
- Big Data
- Deep Learning
- Supervised Learning
- Unsupervised Learning
- Natural Language Processing (NLP)
- Recognition Numbers, Text, Image, Sounds

Other examples of Artificial Intelligence

- Google Assistant, Siri, Alexa (Voice Assistants)
- ChatGPT (Virtual Assistants)
- Smart Robots
- Computer Vision
- Autonomous Cars
- Route Planning
- Genetic Algorithms
- Expert Systems
- Decision Making
- Machine Learning
- Knowledge Representation
- Personalized Online Recommendations

Computational Thinking Examples

- Abstraction

- Decomposition
- Pattern Recognition
- Algorithm
- Logical Reasoning
- Critical Thinking
- Troubleshooting
- Algorithmic Thinking

The initial and final interviews were audio recorded, last approximately 10 minutes each and have their own structure, related to the topic under study and which contributes to the assessment of students and the impact of the activity (Amado, 2014). The sample was 10 students from a 9th grade class, based on the knowledge of block programming, which these students generally already have and by including emerging technologies in the essential learning of Information and Communication Technologies of the school year, among others the AI. This class is made up of eighteen students, 10 of whom participated in the study, six females and four males, aged between 14 and 16 years old. This investigation took place at a public basic and secondary school, firstly including an initial interview and at the end of the activity, the final interview using a previous script and a brief introduction to AI and machine learning. Next, the activity that created a project as a machine learning model in ML4K was carried out. It was carried out in a computer room, which has the necessary and appropriate technological resources for carrying out the activity. The activity lasted approximately 90 minutes, and students were divided into 5 groups of 2 students. Each group created their machine learning image recognition model in ML4K, capturing the three hand shapes through a webcam and thus introducing training data, performing learning with testing and importing the model into ML4K's Scratch3. Then, in order to simplify the construction of code blocks, they selected the template (among others) for the Rock Paper Scissors game, existing on the platform. The students modified the code blocks, strictly necessary to run the game, with the previously created learning model and tested it. Throughout the activity, machine learning concepts were related to the pillars of the CT – Problem decomposition, Pattern recognition (prominent in the learning model), Abstraction, Algorithm and also concepts associated with the CT.

Fig. 4. Learning project phases

Figure 4 shows the Train, Learn & Test and Make (Model import) phases in ML4K.

Fig. 5. Learning Model Categories

Figure 5 shows the Rock Paper Scissors categories with their associated images. The template includes standards for each category.

Fig. 6. Project imported into Scratch3 and with blocks added from the Learning Model

Figure 6 shows the ML4k Scratch3 project, with the specific blocks of the learning model, as well as other blocks necessary for image capture. The execution of the Rock Paper Scissors game project is based on events between the different authors

Fig. 7. Execution of the project in Scratch3

Figure 7 shows an execution of the project, with the rules of the game, in which there is movement of the player, in this case of scissors and the computer - rock, and the respective result - you lose, is presented.

Fig. 8. Students in the testing phase of the ML4K learning model.

Figure 8 shows students testing the learning model in ML4K.

VII. DATA ANALYSIS

The data analysis presented in this article aims to answer specific questions related to the study.

Fig. 9. Results obtained in the Initial / Final interview

We found, through the initial interview, that 10% of the students knew automatic learning or machine learning. At the end of the activity, 100% of the students acquired the concepts mentioned above.

Fig. 10. Results obtained in the Initial / Final interview

The concept of Artificial Intelligence was mentioned by 100% of students as having knowledge.

Fig. 11. Results obtained in the Initial / Final interview

In the initial interview, 10% of the students had knowledge about the CT and in the final interview, everyone indicated that they already knew.

Can you provide examples of machine learning ?

Description	Number of Students
Master Algorithm	1
Decision Tree	0
Neural networks	0
Big Data	0
Deep Learning	0
Supervised Learning	0
Unsupervised Learning	0
Natural language processing	0
Number and text recognition	1

Tabela I
RESULTS OBTAINED IN THE INITIAL INTERVIEW

In the initial interview, only one student indicated examples of machine learning.

Description	Number of Students
Master Algorithm	6
Decision Tree	0
Neural networks	0
Big Data	1
Deep Learning	1
Supervised learning	0
Unsupervised learning	0
Natural language processing	0
Number and text recognition	9

Tabela II
RESULTS OBTAINED IN THE FINAL INTERVIEW

In the final interview, most students indicated number and text recognition as examples, followed by the Master Algorithm, Big Data and Deep Learning.

Fig. 12. Artificial Intelligence

Examples of Google Assistant, Siri, Alexa, followed by intelligent robots were mentioned by students in the initial and final interviews and in the final interview 3 students identified machine learning.

Fig. 13. Pillars and concepts of Computational Thinking

In the initial interview, only 1 student identified the 4 pillars of the CT. In the final interview, all students identified the pillars Abstraction, Decomposition and Algorithm and 8 students gave Pattern Recognition as an example. Four students indicated Problem Solving as a pillar of CT and 1 student indicated Algorithmic Thinking.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained and relating to (Caruso & Cavalheiro, 2021) in which “programming projects applying AI are a powerful tool in CT development. Based on the statistical analysis of the responses to questionnaires administered before and after students participated in the workshops with LearningML, there was a significant improvement in learning concepts regarding AI.” In this sense, the results obtained indicate that this study was

an added value and could be a promising and innovative approach to the teaching and learning of AI and the development of the CT. In the analysis carried out between the use of the platform and the ML4K tool with the CT, it is concluded that ML4K is a valuable contribution to teaching the CT. As future work, we plan to use the ML4K platform in the 3rd cycle and Secondary, with activities related to the AI context, promoting the development of the CT.

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